

Smarandache's Orthic Theorem

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Abstract.

We present the Smarandache's Orthic Theorem in the geometry of the triangle.

Smarandache's Orthic Theorem.

Given a triangle ABC whose angles are all acute (acute triangle), we consider $A'B'C'$, the triangle formed by the legs of its altitudes.

In which conditions the expression:

$$\|A'B'\| \cdot \|B'C'\| + \|B'C'\| \cdot \|C'A'\| + \|C'A'\| \cdot \|A'B'\|$$

is maximum?

Proof.

We have

$$\triangle ABC \sim \triangle A'B'C' \sim \triangle AB'C \sim \triangle A'BC' \tag{1}$$

We note

$$\|BA'\| = x, \|CB'\| = y, \|AC'\| = z.$$

It results that

$$\|A'C'\| = a-x, \|B'A'\| = b-y, \|C'B'\| = c-z$$

$$\widehat{BAC} = \widehat{B'A'C} = \widehat{BA'C'}; \widehat{ABC} = \widehat{AB'C'} = \widehat{A'B'C'}; \widehat{BCA} = \widehat{BC'A'} = \widehat{B'C'A}$$

From these equalities it results the relation (1)

$$\Delta A'BC' \sim \Delta A'B'C \Rightarrow \frac{\|A'C'\|}{a-x} = \frac{x}{\|A'B'\|} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta A'B'C \sim \Delta AB'C' \Rightarrow \frac{\|A'C'\|}{z} = \frac{c-z}{\|B'C'\|} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta AB'C' \sim \Delta A'B'C \Rightarrow \frac{\|B'C'\|}{y} = \frac{b-y}{\|A'B'\|} \quad (4)$$

From (2), (3) and (4) we observe that the sum of the products from the problem is equal to:

$$x(a-x) + y(b-y) + z(c-z) = \frac{1}{4}(a^2 + b^2 + c^2) - \left(x - \frac{a}{2}\right)^2 - \left(y - \frac{b}{2}\right)^2 - \left(z - \frac{c}{2}\right)^2$$

which will reach its maximum as long as $x = \frac{a}{2}$, $y = \frac{b}{2}$, $z = \frac{c}{2}$, that is when the altitudes' legs are in the middle of the sides, therefore when the ΔABC is equilateral. The maximum of the expression is $\frac{1}{4}(a^2 + b^2 + c^2)$.

Conclusion (Smarandache's Orthic Theorem):

If we note the lengths of the sides of the triangle ΔABC by $\|AB\| = c$, $\|BC\| = a$, $\|CA\| = b$, and the lengths of the sides of its orthic triangle $\Delta A'B'C'$ by $\|A'B'\| = c'$, $\|B'C'\| = a'$, $\|C'A'\| = b'$, then we proved that:

$$4(a'b' + b'c' + c'a') \leq a^2 + b^2 + c^2.$$

Open Problems related to Smarandache's Orthic Theorem:

1. Generalize this problem to polygons. Let $A_1A_2\dots A_m$ be a polygon and P a point inside it. From P we draw perpendiculars on each side A_iA_{i+1} of the polygon and we note by A_i' the intersection between the perpendicular and the side A_iA_{i+1} . A pedal polygon $A_1'A_2'\dots A_m'$ is formed. What properties does this pedal polygon have?
2. Generalize this problem to polyhedrons. Let $A_1A_2\dots A_n$ be a polyhedron and P a point inside it. From P we draw perpendiculars on each polyhedron face F_i and we note by A_i' the intersection between the perpendicular and the side F_i . A pedal polyhedron $A_1'A_2'\dots A_p'$ is formed, where p is the number of polyhedron's faces. What properties does this pedal polyhedron have?

References:

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